

PSSOH 2024 CONFERENCE AGENDA

Date: October 12, 2024

Place: amfiteater 56, building of Technical faculties ([University of Belgrade – School of Electrical Engineering](#)), ground floor, Bulevar kralja Aleksandra 73, 11000 Belgrade Serbia

CET	Lecturer	Talk
10:00	ETF Dean Prof. Dejan Gvozdić	Welcome note
10:05 – 10:20	PSSOH Editor Assist. Prof. Miloš Bjelić	The Seventh PSSOH: Editorial Board Perspective
PLENARY SESSION		
10:20 – 11:20	Ljiljana Lazarević	Meta-science - how to improve science using science
11:20 – 12:40	BRUNCH BREAK	
PSSOH SESSION WITH INVITED LECTURES Moderator: PSSOH Editor Assoc. Prof. Miloš Cvetanović		
12:40 – 13:00	Bogdan Brković, Milovan Majstorović, Mateja Ivanović, and Mladen Terzić	Switched reluctance motor drive simulation using open-source software
13:00 – 13:20	Aleksandar Ćirić	Review of open software for applications in optical spectroscopy
13:20 – 13:40	Aleksandar Knežević	Analysis of flight performance and gaze behavior indicators in flight simulators of varying fidelity using free software tools
13:40 – 14:00	Nikolina Škorić	Overview of Selected Free Software Tools for Video and Audio Editing
14:00	PSSOH Editor Assoc. Prof. Nadica Miljković	Conference Closing

